

Pediatric Acute Abdomen: Coexistence of Mature Ovarian Teratoma and Reactive Appendicitis. A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Acute abdominal pain in childhood represents a frequent diagnostic challenge in pediatrics. Acute appendicitis is the most common surgical cause; however, in premenarchal girls, gynecological pathologies such as ovarian teratomas—benign germ cell tumors that may remain asymptomatic or present with symptoms once complications arise—should also be included in the differential diagnosis.

Materials and Methods: We report the case of an 11-year-old patient presenting with acute abdominal pain. Clinical evaluation was complemented by imaging studies; ultrasound, non-contrast and contrast-enhanced computed tomography, that revealed a mature cystic ovarian teratoma associated with a reactive appendiceal inflammatory process.

Results: The patient underwent surgical intervention consisting of teratoma resection and appendectomy. Postoperative recovery was successful, with no complications.

Discussion and Conclusions: This case highlights the relevance of a multidisciplinary approach in the evaluation of acute abdomen, where imaging plays a pivotal role in achieving diagnostic accuracy. The coexistence of gynecological pathology with reactive appendiceal involvement underscores the need to consider non-gastrointestinal causes. Incorporating gynecological assessment into pediatric diagnostic protocols is essential to ensure comprehensive care, safeguard reproductive health, and improve long-term outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Acute abdominal pain, Reactive appendicitis, Mature ovarian teratoma, Diagnostic imaging, Multidisciplinary approach.

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INTRODUCTION

Abdominal pain is defined as an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience localized to the region between the thorax and pelvis. It results from the activation of nerve

receptors located in internal organs, the abdominal wall, or adjacent structures. Based on its pathophysiological mechanism, abdominal pain can be classified as visceral, somatic, or referred.¹ It represents one of the most frequent

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reasons for consultation, with an estimated prevalence of 40% in outpatient visits and 5–25% of emergency hospital admissions.^{2,3} Owing to its nonspecific nature, abdominal pain poses a considerable diagnostic challenge; in up to 60% of cases, the final diagnosis remains unclear, and in 35–43% of patients, it is limited to “abdominal pain under evaluation.”^{4,5}

This wide spectrum of etiologies makes abdominal pain a significant diagnostic challenge in the emergency setting. Among the most relevant causes is acute appendicitis, one of the leading surgical emergencies worldwide. Prompt identification is critical, as early diagnosis significantly reduces morbidity and prevents potentially life-threatening complications such as perforation and peritonitis.^{6,7}

On the other hand, appendicitis is defined as an acute inflammatory process of the cecal appendix, a narrow tubular structure arising from the cecum, the initial portion of the colon. Inflammation is usually triggered by luminal obstruction, most commonly due to fecaliths, lymphoid hyperplasia, foreign bodies, or infections. Obstruction increases intraluminal pressure, compromises blood flow, promotes bacterial proliferation, and may progress to necrosis and perforation of the appendiceal wall, with subsequent risk of peritonitis if not promptly treated.^{8,9}

In addition to gastrointestinal causes, gynecological etiologies must also be considered, particularly in prepubertal and peripubertal female patients, in whom adnexal pathologies may be relevant. Among these, mature cystic ovarian teratoma, also known as dermoid cyst, is one of the most common benign ovarian tumors in childhood and adolescence, accounting for 10–20% of pediatric ovarian masses.¹⁰

These teratomas are characterized by the presence of tissues derived from the three germ layers: ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm. They typically grow slowly and remain asymptomatic, often diagnosed at advanced stages or when associated with complications such as ovarian torsion, rupture, or infection. However, due to their proximity to structures such as the cecal appendix, they may exert a mass effect that, through anatomic contiguity and peritoneal irritation, induces a secondary inflammatory response in the appendix, a phenomenon described as reactive appendicitis.¹¹ The coexistence of an ovarian teratoma and appendiceal inflammation poses a diagnostic challenge, as the clinical presentation may mimic classic acute appendicitis, leading to an exclusively gastrointestinal approach while overlooking a potential gynecological etiology. This underscores the importance of thorough evaluation using imaging techniques such as pelvic ultrasound, particularly in premenarchal patients with nonspecific abdominal symptoms.

Epidemiology and Clinical Relevance.

Abdominal pain in pediatrics represents a constant diagnostic challenge due to its high prevalence and wide range of causes. It is estimated that 5–25% of pediatric emergency department visits are related to this condition, with acute appendicitis

being the leading surgical emergency in children.^{12,13} However, in female patients approaching puberty, gynecological pathologies such as ovarian teratomas may coexist with or mimic abdominal inflammatory processes, complicating the diagnostic approach.

Ovarian tumors in girls are uncommon, with an incidence of 2.2 per 100,000, accounting for only 2–3% of all pediatric cancers.¹⁴ Among these, teratomas derived from pluripotent germ cells constitute 20–25% of ovarian neoplasms, the majority of which are mature and benign.¹⁵

A Colombian study described 17 pediatric patients with ovarian teratomas, with a mean age of 11.4 years, predominance on the right side in 64.7%, and a palpable mass in 65%.¹⁴ This profile closely matches that of the present patient, who, at 11 years of age, presented with right hypochondrial pain that progressed to generalized pain with emphasis on the right iliac fossa.

Etiology and Classification of Teratoma and Appendicitis.

Ovarian teratomas originate from germ cells capable of differentiating into tissues from all three embryonic layers: ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm.¹⁶ These tumors are classified as mature (benign) or immature (with malignant potential). Although slow-growing, they may cause complications such as ovarian torsion, rupture, or compression of adjacent organs, including the cecal appendix. In parallel, acute appendicitis is defined as an inflammatory process of the cecal appendix, usually secondary to luminal obstruction, with a risk of necrosis and perforation if not promptly managed.¹⁷ The coexistence of an ovarian teratoma with appendiceal inflammation—whether reactive or primary—is rare but has been reported.

Clinical Manifestations.

Most teratomas remain asymptomatic until they reach a considerable size or develop complications. Ovarian torsion is the most common complication, typically presenting as acute abdominal pain. For example, Tsai et al. (2011)¹⁸ reported the case of a 5-year-old girl with ovarian torsion secondary to a teratoma mimicking perforated appendicitis. In Australia, Pinto and Hool (2023)¹⁹ described a giant ovarian teratoma that clinically resembled complicated appendicitis. Similarly, Mata et al. (2015)²⁰ documented the coexistence of perforated appendicitis and a giant ovarian cyst. In the present case, the patient presented with nausea, bilious vomiting, and localized pain that progressed to signs of peritoneal irritation, including a positive McBurney’s sign. Abdominal ultrasound is the recommended initial tool for evaluating adnexal masses and appendicitis, complemented by computed tomography (CT) in cases of diagnostic uncertainty.¹⁴ In this case, ultrasound revealed a right adnexal mass measuring 82 × 58 × 77 mm with echogenic features suggestive of a mature teratoma, and an inflamed but compressible cecal appendix without evidence of appendicolith. The importance of differential diagnosis is emphasized by Royo Trallero et al. (2020),¹¹ who highlighted

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the diagnostic challenges when these entities coexist, given possible clinical–radiological discordance. Furthermore, recent reports indicate that ovarian teratomas may extend into the right iliac fossa, mimicking complicated or perforated appendicitis.^{21,22}

Diagnostic Imaging Approach.

Imaging plays a fundamental role in the evaluation of patients with acute abdominal pain, particularly in young females, where gynecological and surgical causes may coexist or simulate one another. In the present case, sequential imaging was crucial in clarifying the dual etiology. Initial transabdominal ultrasound identified a right adnexal mass with heterogeneous components, suggestive of a mature ovarian teratoma. However, visualization of the appendix was inconclusive, prompting non-contrast abdominopelvic CT, which revealed mural thickening and periappendiceal inflammatory changes consistent with appendicitis, as well as confirming the ovarian teratoma. Subsequent contrast-enhanced CT further characterized the adnexal mass, demonstrating adipose tissue, calcifications, and dental structures—typical findings of mature teratomas.^{23,24}

This combination of imaging techniques not only enabled the simultaneous identification of both pathologies but also allowed for appropriate surgical planning, minimizing risks and optimizing therapeutic management. Evidence suggests that a stepwise imaging strategy—including ultrasound, non-contrast CT, and contrast-enhanced CT—significantly improves diagnostic accuracy in complex clinical scenarios such as the coexistence of ovarian teratoma with reactive or primary appendicitis.²⁵

Clinical management and prognosis.

The standard treatment for mature teratomas is ovarian cystectomy, with preservation of functional ovarian tissue. Clinical follow-up includes endocrinological assessment to monitor pubertal development and fertility, as well as oncological surveillance in cases with immature features.¹⁴

In this case, surgical intervention allowed resection of the teratomatous mass and exploration of the appendix, which revealed a reactive inflammatory process without perforation.

Clinical Implications and Relevance of the Case.

This case highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in girls with abdominal pain, considering both gastrointestinal and gynecological pathologies. Regional and international literature concur that early diagnosis prevents severe complications such as ovarian torsion or progression of appendiceal inflammation.^{6,14}

The experience from this intervention underscores the need to include these entities in the differential diagnosis of pediatric female acute abdomen, as well as the relevance of timely and appropriate imaging evaluation to guide optimal therapeutic planning.

JUSTIFICATION

This study arises from the need to document and analyze uncommon clinical cases in the pediatric population, such as the coexistence of a mature cystic ovarian teratoma and an appendiceal inflammatory process. This condition represents a diagnostic challenge in the evaluation of acute abdominal pain in premenarchal girls, as its clinical similarity to classic acute appendicitis may lead to incomplete or inadequate treatment if adnexal pathologies are not considered in the differential diagnosis.

The limited literature available on the association between ovarian teratomas and reactive appendicitis restricts clinicians' ability to recognize such cases in a timely manner. The relevance of this study lies in providing clinical evidence to raise awareness within the medical community about the need to integrate a gynecological perspective in the evaluation of acute abdomen in pediatrics. It also emphasizes the pivotal role of imaging as a diagnostic tool to distinguish between gastrointestinal and gynecological pathologies.

The knowledge generated will help optimize diagnostic and therapeutic processes in patients with atypical clinical presentations, supporting appropriate surgical interventions, preservation of ovarian function, and reduction of complications such as ovarian torsion or progression to peritonitis.

OBJECTIVE

To comprehensively describe and analyze the clinical, imaging, and surgical characteristics of the coexistence of a mature cystic ovarian teratoma and acute appendicitis in a pediatric patient, based on a detailed review of a clinical case documented at the General Hospital of Cancún over a six-month period.

Specific Objectives

- To identify the distinctive clinical features present in a pediatric patient with acute abdomen due to the coexistence of a mature ovarian teratoma and reactive appendicitis.
- To systematize relevant imaging findings that facilitated the differential diagnosis.
- To describe the surgical approach employed and its outcomes.
- To compare the case with available scientific literature in order to propose a standardized diagnostic pathway.
- To generate useful evidence for the differential diagnosis and therapeutic management of similar cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Study Design.

An observational, descriptive study was conducted in the form of a clinical case report. The primary objective was to comprehensively document and analyze the diagnostic and therapeutic approach in a premenarchal pediatric patient

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presenting simultaneously with a mature cystic ovarian teratoma and a reactive appendiceal inflammatory process.

Data Collection Plan.

Clinical, imaging, surgical, and histopathological information was retrospectively collected from the patient's electronic and paper medical records at the Pediatric Service of the General Hospital of Cancún "Jesús Kumate Rodríguez," from hospital admission on January 14, 2025, through outpatient postoperative follow-up three weeks after discharge.

Sociodemographic variables, personal and family history, clinical findings and progression, laboratory and imaging results (ultrasound, non-contrast and contrast-enhanced computed tomography), and surgical and histopathological findings were included.

Data Analysis Plan

The obtained data were organized and systematized using a chronological clinical narrative. A descriptive qualitative analysis with a clinical-radiological focus was performed to establish the temporal relationship between symptom progression and integrate clinical findings with imaging, surgical, and histopathological correlation, in accordance with standards for a multidisciplinary approach in the evaluation of pediatric acute abdomen and current recommendations for differential gynecological diagnosis in the assessment of adnexal masses in premenarchal girls.

Operationalization of Variables

The clinical, diagnostic, and imaging variables deemed relevant for case analysis are detailed in Table 1, located in Appendix I, specifying their operational definitions, type, and collection method.

CASE REPORT

An 11-year-old female patient, born and residing in Cancún, Quintana Roo, enrolled in the 6th grade of primary school, with no history of allergies, prior surgeries, or chronic-degenerative diseases, reported no menarche or sexual activity. Blood type was O Rh positive. Her mother, 29 years old, was a housewife with overweight and type 2 diabetes mellitus; her father, 33 years old, was a taxi driver with no relevant medical history.

On the morning of January 13, 2025, the patient experienced sudden-onset abdominal pain, initially localized to the right hypochondrium, associated with gastrointestinal vomiting. Six hours later, she sought care at a primary healthcare facility, where she received a single oral dose of trimebutine (10 mL) and intramuscular metoclopramide (5 mg), resulting in partial symptom improvement with cessation of vomiting

but persistent abdominal pain. An abdominal ultrasound performed the same day at an external facility reported findings compatible with acute appendicitis. The patient was not admitted and returned home due to her parents decision.

Due to persistent generalized pain 24 hours after onset, she presented to the pediatric emergency department of the General Hospital of Cancún, reporting generalized abdominal pain radiating to the right iliac fossa, unrelated to food intake. Nausea and bilious vomiting recurred, up to four episodes, with no urinary symptoms or fever.

Physical examination in the emergency department revealed normal vital signs. The patient was ambulatory, with intermittent support from a family member, showing an algic facial expression and antalgic posture. Glasgow Coma Scale was 15. Oral mucosa was dry, with mild pallor of the skin. Abdominal examination revealed mild distension, voluntary guarding, tenderness on deep palpation in the right hypochondrium and right iliac fossa, muscular resistance, a positive McBurney's sign, and reduced bowel sounds. She was admitted within 30 minutes to the pediatric service for observation and diagnostic workup. Laboratory studies performed within 20 minutes of admission revealed a mildly elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) of 1.3 mg/dL; other parameters were within normal limits: hemoglobin 14.1 g/dL, hematocrit 41.1%, leukocytes $10.9 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$ (10,900/ μL), neutrophils 67%, platelets $360 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, and a normal urinalysis.

A follow-up abdominal ultrasound on January 14, 2025, eight hours after admission, revealed a distended gallbladder with anechoic content and thin walls (Figure 1); mild dilation of the right renal pelvis and calyces, with preserved vascular flow on color Doppler (Figure 2); and, upon multiple targeted scans of the right iliac fossa, a right adnexal unilocular, ovoid, well-circumscribed, complex mass with mixed echogenicity and solid components measuring 47×30 mm. The mass contained fat echogenicity and a 4 mm calcified nodule, with an echogenic interface at the border causing posterior acoustic shadowing. Overall, the mass measured $82 \times 58 \times 77$ mm with an estimated volume of 195 mL (Figure 3). Due to a poorly distended bladder, acoustic windows were limited, preventing complete delineation of the mass and its interface with the ipsilateral ovary.

Adjacent to the right ovary, in close contact, the cecal appendix was identified with increased echogenicity of the surrounding fat and a present "target sign" (Figure 4). The appendix was compressible, 8 mm in diameter, with no evidence of appendicolith, showing features suggestive of an inflammatory process, likely due to contiguity, and no observable lymphadenopathy.

Figure 1. Grayscale abdominal ultrasound showing the gallbladder in its normal anatomical position with normal sonographic features.

Figure 2. (a) Grayscale ultrasound of the right kidney showing mild dilation of the intrarenal pelvis and central calyces; (b) renal blood flow demonstrated on color Doppler.

Figure 3. Pelvic ultrasound of the right adnexal region in longitudinal (a) and transverse (b) planes, showing a unilocular, complex mass with mixed fat–fluid echogenicity, a calcified nodule, Color Doppler score 1, with an estimated volume of 195 mL.

Figure 4. Ultrasound of the right iliac fossa in transverse view (a) and magnified view (b), showing a non-compressible cecal appendix with submucosal thickening (asterisk), loss of the mucosal layer, collapse of the appendiceal lumen (thick arrow), diameter 8 mm (calipers), and increased echogenicity of the mesoappendiceal fat (star).

The right adnexal mass observed on ultrasound exhibited complex features highly suggestive of an ovarian teratoma, specifically a dermoid cyst, which is the most common ovarian neoplasm with heterogeneous content, including fat and calcifications. However, the presence of a 4 mm calcification and solid components further supports the suspicion of a mature teratoma. Although the echogenic interface at the border and the difficulty in fully delineating the mass from the ovary may indicate that the mass is in contact with or adherent to the ovary, the exact relationship could not be precisely defined on this examination.

Close contact with the cecal appendix, increased echogenicity of the surrounding fat, an 8 mm diameter, and the presence of inflammatory signs (target sign) suggest a periappendiceal inflammatory process, likely acute appendicitis or localized periappendiceal inflammation. The absence of appendicolith and lymphadenopathy reduces the likelihood of severe complications, although clear inflammatory changes were present. Mild intrarenal dilation may be secondary to compression by the adnexal mass affecting the renal

collecting system or other obstructive processes; preserved vascular flow on Doppler indicates no acute ischemia or vascular torsion. A gallbladder with normal sonographic features ruled out additional inflammatory processes and other differential diagnoses in the context of abdominal pain. The patient was evaluated by the pediatric surgery service 10 hours after hospital admission and showed no signs of systemic inflammatory response or acute abdomen that would indicate the need for urgent surgical intervention. Therefore, additional studies were requested, including tumor markers and contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic computed tomography (CT).

Two hours later, a contrast-enhanced CT scan with iodinated intravenous contrast was performed, which better characterized the lesion. The study revealed a mass measuring 84 × 91 × 85 mm, with a volume of 336 mL, showing a fluid-fat level (-42 HU) (Figure 5), intralesional calcification (861 HU) (Figure 6) measuring 11 × 10 mm, and fine septa less than 1 mm, without contrast enhancement, highly suggestive of an ovarian teratoma.

Figure 5. Contrast-enhanced axial (a and b) and sagittal (c) abdominopelvic CT in soft tissue window, showing a well-defined right adnexal complex mass composed of a cystic portion (asterisk) and a fatty portion (star), with fine internal septa of 1 mm and no post-contrast enhancement.

Figure 6. Contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT in axial (a), coronal (b), and sagittal (c) planes, soft tissue window, showing a complex right adnexal mass with a small calcific focus (861 HU) on the medial–left aspect (arrows).

Figure 7. Contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT in axial (a and b) and coronal (c) planes, soft tissue window, showing the cecal appendix (arrows) measuring 8 mm in the right iliac fossa, in close contact with a complex right adnexal mass.

The study highlighted the mass’s close contact with the cecal appendix (Figure 7), which was displaced toward the pelvis, showing stranding of the pericecal fat and a small amount of fluid in the ipsilateral iliac fossa, findings compatible with secondary inflammation due to compression or contiguity.

Correlation with the relevant imaging findings obtained from the different imaging modalities performed in the patient indicated that computed tomography (CT) provided better characterization of the previously described sonographic findings. The right adnexal mass demonstrated features of a complex cyst with lipid components, fine septa, and intralesional calcification, which is highly suggestive of a dermoid cyst or ovarian teratoma (teratoid cyst). The presence of fatty content, calcification, fine septa, and adnexal location supports this interpretation. The proximity and mild inflammation of the cecal appendix may indicate a secondary inflammatory complication, such as appendicitis or reactive periappendiceal inflammation.

Important considerations in this case include the absence of active vascularization or post-contrast enhancement, supporting a benign or low-aggressiveness nature. Intralesional calcification may correspond to bony structures, teeth, or calcified tissue within the cyst. The difficulty in clearly delineating the interface with the ovary may result from close contact or perilesional inflammation. These findings corroborate that the lesion represents a complex dermoid cyst (ovarian teratoma) in the right ovary, with cystic, fatty, and calcified components, consistent with a benign germ cell tumor. Its relationship with adjacent structures, particularly the cecal appendix, and

periappendiceal inflammation should be considered in the clinical and surgical assessment.

Tumor markers were assessed 11 hours after hospital admission: beta-human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) was negative, ruling out pregnancy and associated conditions; alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) <0.50 ng/mL; carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) <0.50 ng/mL; CA 125 10.8 U/mL; CA 19-9 mildly elevated at 46.58 U/mL; and CA 15-3 8 U/mL. Most tumor markers were within normal limits, except for a slight elevation of CA 19-9. In a prepubertal girl, these markers generally have limited diagnostic value without specific symptoms. Mild elevation may be incidental or reflect benign or inflammatory processes and should be interpreted in the context of clinical history, physical examination, and other diagnostic studies, as in this case.

The Pediatric Appendicitis Score (PAS) was low (2 points), indicating a low probability of acute appendicitis at that time, emphasizing the need for a multidisciplinary approach. Despite initial clinical stability, 23 hours after admission, the patient developed fever (38.5°C), increased colicky abdominal pain—persistent, constant, and apparently localized to the right iliac fossa—and elevated acute-phase reactants. Laboratory values reported during the night shift on January 14, 2025, showed: hemoglobin 15.1 g/dL, hematocrit 44.2%; leukocytosis $13.9 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$; neutrophilia with 70.4% segmented neutrophils (absolute $2884 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$); platelets $328 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$; prothrombin time 11.4 seconds; partial thromboplastin time 30.5 seconds; INR 1.01—all within normal limits.

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Given equivocal clinical signs of acute appendicitis, laboratory and imaging studies suggestive of a periappendiceal process, and the incidental right adnexal mass, prophylactic antibiotics and intravenous analgesia were administered. On January 15, 2025, an exploratory laparotomy was performed, including resection of the right adnexal tumor, right salpingo-oophorectomy, and appendectomy.

Surgical findings included a normothermic abdominal cavity, a heterogeneous tumor arising from the right ovary measuring approximately 12 × 12 cm (Figure 8), minimal free fluid in the abdominal cavity, uterus measuring 7 × 3 cm, macroscopically normal left ovary, and a cecal appendix in pelvic position measuring 8 × 0.5 cm, without edema or erythema and with intact base. The specimens were sent to the clinical pathology department for histopathological evaluation.

Figure 8. Surgical specimen obtained from exploratory laparotomy and resection of the right adnexal tumor. The tumor arose from the right ovary, with histopathological diagnosis of a mature cystic teratoma (benign) containing a small area of hemorrhage.

During the postoperative period, the patient remained hemodynamically stable, without abdominal distension, tolerating a regular diet, free of nausea or vomiting, and with normal bowel movements. She was discharged 96 hours after surgery with instructions for a regular diet avoiding irritants and maintaining adequate hydration.

The patient was re-evaluated by the pediatric surgery service three weeks after hospital discharge, with no reported clinical complications. The histopathological study was reported 20 days after hospital admission (Figure 9), revealing a mature cystic teratoma (benign) of the right ovary with a small area of hemorrhage and an inflamed cecal appendix, without evidence of perforation or necrosis.

Figure 9. Timeline: Clinical evolution and treatment.

This clinical case is presented with a primary focus on radiological intervention, which proved essential in managing a complex scenario involving a premenarchal patient with evident clinicoradiological discordance. Imaging played a

pivotal role in this critical context, where timely and accurate diagnosis can mean the difference between successful recovery and serious complications. Radiology contributed significantly to the identification, characterization, and

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surgical planning of both the ovarian mass and the coexisting inflammatory appendiceal process.

The importance of imaging lies in several key dimensions, providing rapid and precise diagnosis of pathologies, lesions, or complications that may not be apparent on clinical examination. This is particularly crucial in hidden pathologies, as exemplified by this case, in which abdominal ultrasound—especially with Doppler—enabled non-invasive, rapid detection of a complex ovarian cyst with lipid components, calcifications, and fine septa, suggestive of a mature teratoma. Additionally, it allowed assessment of the relationship with adjacent structures, such as the cecal appendix, and identification of signs of periappendiceal inflammation.

Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) further delineated the mass, confirming its cystic and fatty content, while also identifying secondary inflammation of the appendix and surrounding tissues. These findings were critical for guiding surgical decision-making and preventing major complications.

In this context, radiology not only provided a precise, non-invasive diagnosis but also directed surgical planning, ensuring appropriate intervention while minimizing risks. This underscores its essential role in the multidisciplinary evaluation of complex pathologies in pediatric patients. As demonstrated by this case, radiology complements clinical assessment and, in many instances, serves as the cornerstone for accurate diagnosis and effective treatment, highlighting its indispensable role in modern medical care.

DISCUSSION

The coexistence of a mature ovarian teratoma with an inflammatory appendiceal process in pediatric patients represents a significant diagnostic challenge due to its clinical similarity to primary acute appendicitis. The typical clinical presentation of right lower quadrant pain, accompanied by nausea and vomiting, often initially guides clinicians toward urgent surgical intervention for suspected appendicitis. However, in premenarchal or adolescent females, gynecological etiologies must be considered in the differential diagnosis.¹¹

The case presented illustrates how an ovarian teratoma, through mass effect or peritoneal irritation, can induce a reactive inflammatory process in the cecal appendix, a phenomenon described as reactive appendicitis. Although uncommon, this condition has been reported in the literature as a consequence of the anatomical proximity between the right ovarian adnexa and the appendix, especially when the mass reaches a considerable size.²⁵

Imaging played a crucial role in the diagnostic approach. Initial abdominal ultrasound identified a complex adnexal mass, although it was limited in defining the precise relationship with the appendix. Computed tomography (CT) provided superior anatomical delineation, revealing periappendiceal inflammation and confirming the features of

a mature teratoma. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), although not always immediately available, is useful for detailed characterization of teratoma components, including adipose tissue, calcifications, and septa.^{23,24}

Simultaneous surgical management of the adnexal mass and appendix was decisive in preventing complications such as ovarian torsion, appendiceal perforation, or peritonitis. Ovarian preservation, when feasible, should be prioritized in the pediatric population to safeguard future reproductive function.¹⁴

Based on the comprehensive analysis of this case and available literature, the following clinical recommendations are proposed for the management of pediatric patients with acute abdominal pain and suspected adnexal masses:

Always maintain a gynecological perspective in premenarchal and adolescent females with acute abdomen, especially when pain is localized in the right lower quadrant, to avoid limiting the diagnosis solely to gastrointestinal causes such as appendicitis.

Implement a stepwise imaging-based diagnostic approach, starting with transabdominal or transvaginal ultrasound, complemented by CT in cases where clinical suspicion or visualization is insufficient, and consider MRI for detailed characterization of complex adnexal masses.

Integrate early multidisciplinary evaluation among pediatrics, pediatric surgery, gynecology, and radiology when adnexal findings or coexistence of periappendiceal inflammatory signs are identified.

Apply validated diagnostic scales, such as the Pediatric Appendicitis Score (PAS), to estimate preoperative appendicitis risk, combined with comprehensive interpretation of imaging studies.

Indicate surgery when there are signs of complications or coexistence of inflammatory processes, prioritizing techniques that allow ovarian preservation whenever possible, especially in patients of reproductive age.

Request tumor markers in the presence of complex adnexal masses; however, in pediatric patients, interpretation should be cautious and always correlated with clinical and imaging context.

Establish institutional protocols for differential diagnosis in pediatric female acute abdomen, including algorithms that facilitate diagnostic and therapeutic decision-making.

CONCLUSION

This clinical case underscores the importance of looking beyond the initial diagnostic impression, particularly in the context of abdominal pain in pediatric patients. The coexistence of an ovarian teratoma with reactive appendicitis not only represented a diagnostic challenge but also provided a valuable learning opportunity regarding the need to integrate clinical evaluation with imaging and multidisciplinary collaboration.

Without a comprehensive imaging-based approach, as employed in this patient, treatment might have been

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incomplete or even inadequate. Each diagnostic modality contributes indispensable detail: ultrasound allows rapid and safe initial assessment, CT delineates anatomical structures and relationships, and MRI provides in-depth characterization that facilitates surgical decision-making.

This case reinforces the critical role of imaging in modern medicine and the necessity of considering gynecological context in premenarchal and adolescent females with acute abdomen. It also highlights the importance of collaborative interdisciplinary care to ensure accurate diagnosis and timely treatment, not only resolving the acute condition but also preserving quality of life and reproductive function.

Beyond a complex case, this experience serves as a reminder that medicine is both a science and an art, requiring careful interpretation of each patient, with each diagnosis representing a story that deserves to be approached with commitment, knowledge, and sensitivity.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This case report was prepared in compliance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, 8th revision,²⁶ and in accordance with current Mexican legal regulations regarding human research, including the General Health Law,²⁷ and the Official Mexican Standard NOM-012-SSA3-2012,²⁸ governing research involving human subjects in Mexico.

The patient is a minor and part of a vulnerable population; therefore, enhanced ethical and legal protections were applied. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents as legal representatives, and verbal assent was obtained from the patient after providing clear, detailed, and understandable information regarding clinical management, diagnostic procedures, imaging studies, and surgical intervention described in this case. The use of the information was strictly for scientific and academic purposes, with written authorization for subsequent publication, ensuring confidentiality of personal data. Participation was voluntary, without incentives, and fully respected the patient's progressive autonomy.

Medical care was conducted under strict clinical indications, adhering closely to the principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, and proportionality of risk. This study does not constitute experimental research. The clinical case is presented retrospectively, without identifying data, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of the patient, in compliance with national data protection laws.

This case is relevant due to the learning opportunity it provides for critical decision-making while safeguarding the principle of beneficence. It is expected that this report will contribute to evidence generation and promote best practices in similar cases.

The case report was reviewed and approved under the guidelines of the Research Committee and the Ethics Committee of the General Hospital of Cancún "Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez," with approval numbers: Dictamen-CI-

2025-013-HGC and Dictamen-CEI-2025-013-HGC, respectively, complying with national and international ethical and legal standards applicable to the scientific dissemination of clinical cases in vulnerable pediatric populations.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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ANNEX I.

Table 1. Operationalization of clinical, diagnostic, and imaging variables considered in the analysis of the case report.

VARIABLE	OPERATIONAL DEFINITION	TYPE	COLLECTION METHOD
Age	Chronological age at the time of hospital admission	Discrete quantitative	Clinical history
Sex	Biological sex assigned at birth	Nominal qualitative	Clinical history
Abdominal pain	Presence and clinical characteristics of pain reported by the patient	Nominal qualitative	Interview, physical examination
Pain location	Anatomical region where the pain was localized (right hypochondrium, right iliac fossa)	Nominal qualitative	Clinical history, physical examination
Adnexal mass	Presence of a tumor characterized by ultrasound and CT	Nominal qualitative	Ultrasound, CT scan
Tumor markers	Serum levels of AFP, β -hCG, CA 125, CA 19-9, CA 15-3	Continuous quantitative	Laboratory results
Imaging diagnosis	Radiological findings based on ultrasound, non-contrast and contrast-enhanced CT	Nominal qualitative	Imaging reports
Surgical diagnosis	Diagnosis established during the surgical intervention	Nominal qualitative	Intraoperative and postoperative notes
Histopathological diagnosis	Result of microscopic analysis of the teratoma and appendix	Nominal qualitative	Pathology report
Postoperative complications	Presence or absence of adverse events during follow-up	Nominal qualitative	Clinical follow-up
Hospital stay	Number of days from admission to hospital discharge	Continuous quantitative	Hospital clinical record